

DETECTION OF A GASEOUS ORGANOPHOSPHORUS COMPOUND USING A SUPPORTED
COPPER + CUPROUS OXIDE ISLAND FILM

EDWARD S. KOLESAR, PhD, P.E., Major, USAF

Air Force Institute of Technology, (AFIT/ENG)
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-6583

ABSTRACT

The electronic properties modified by the exposure of a dielectric supported island film of copper + cuprous oxide to small concentrations (ppm levels) of diisopropyl methylphosphonate (DIMP) is reported. Electron microscopy and electron diffraction measurements confirmed the film's structure and composition. Auger spectroscopy verified the absorption of DIMP. Isothermal direct current measurements suggest a space-charge conduction mechanism whereby carriers are thermally excited, field induced, and transported via shallow trapping and impurity centers.

INTRODUCTION

One critical group of environmental contaminants are the organophosphorus pesticides and structurally affiliated compounds. These materials are unique among contaminants because their distribution is essential for their efficacy. Adding to their impact, these compounds are synthesized and valued for their deleterious effect and persistence. Consequently, there is a need for personal monitoring instrumentation to detect sub-threshold levels of these toxic compounds.

A significant portion of the environmentally sensitive organophosphorus compounds contain either the phosphoryl or thiophosphoryl group. Since diisopropyl methylphosphonate (DIMP) is a phosphoryl-containing compound, has low toxicity, and has been used in a number of previous studies concerned with the detection of gaseous organophosphorus compounds, it was used as a model compound in this investigation [1].

This paper reports the electronic properties that are modified when a dielectric-supported, island morphology, copper + cuprous oxide film is exposed to small concentrations (ppm levels) of DIMP. The motivation for analyzing the film's gas

sensitivity was inspired by prior reported phenomena.

Several researchers cite the use of copper complexes to catalytically hydrolyze phosphorus esters [2,3]. The most significant study is from Wagner-Jauregg, et al [2]. They found that Cu(II) salts catalyze the hydrolysis of diisopropyl phosphonate. The overall reaction occurs in two steps. First, the copper complex binds the phosphorus ester reversibly. Second, the adduct-product is irreversibly broken down by hydrolysis. The property of the first reaction is most useful in this effort. That is, copper complexes may absorb and desorb phosphorus esters in air. The second reaction is less likely to occur on the surface of a copper complex exposed to ambient air because of the low concentration of water.

It is well documented that many of the developmental problems associated with integrated circuit processing can be traced to impurity contamination. A material's surface and electronic properties are strongly influenced by ambient conditions, but little progress has been made exploiting this phenomenon for the practical application of gas detection. Numerous investigators have reported that a discontinuous metallic film's electrical conductivity is modified when it is removed from its high-vacuum deposition chamber and exposed to the atmosphere [4]. The following possibilities, either acting alone or synergistically, may be attributable as the cause for the change in the electronic transport properties:

1. The ambient atmosphere may induce a chemical reaction that results in an irreversible structural modification (for example, oxidation, reduction, or the alteration of surface stress or strain).
2. The ambient atmosphere may be absorbed on the metallic islands and form a surface di-

pole layer which modifies the charge carrier's tunneling barrier height, or be absorbed in the gap region and alter the dielectric's trap density.

The sorption-desorption reversibility characteristic associated with the changes observed in the electrical conductivity of the copper + cuprous oxide island films suggests that the second mechanism dominates the electronic transport process.

The thermally evaporated, discontinuous copper + cuprous oxide films utilized in this detection scheme have a large-valued resistance (typically $10^6 - 10^8$ ohms). A planar, two-terminal, direct current sensing device was fabricated to evaluate the gas-sensitive film's performance.

SENSOR FABRICATION

The sensors were fabricated using standard integrated circuit processing techniques. Glass microscope slides were used as the substrate for the devices. A vacuum thermal evaporation system was utilized to deposit the device electrodes and gas-sensitive discontinuous metallic film. High purity (99.999 percent) copper wire was used as the source for the surface electrodes and gas-sensitive film. A piezoelectric quartz crystal thickness monitor was utilized to control the evaporation rate (typically $3-5 \text{ \AA} \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$) and monitor the average thickness of a deposition.

Metal masks were used to define electrode arrangements and control the coverage of the copper + cuprous oxide films. Electrode gaps of 203 and 508 microns were utilized to obtain practical values of the gas sensitive film's resistance. Figure 1 depicts a 203 micron wide electrode gap sensor.

INSTRUMENTATION

The application of a direct current bias to the gas-sensitive film was accomplished using a battery source and an electrometer was used to measure the film's resistance.

The dynamic gas generation and delivery system is illustrated in Figure 2. A critical element in this system is the DIMP permeation tube [5]. When operated at 50°C , a broad concentration range spanning 0.1-650 ppm of DIMP is available.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical Characteristics. Two critical issues concerning the operation of the sensor are the physical structure and composition of the thermally-evaporated, gas-sensitive film, and verification that DIMP is absorbed. Physical structure and composition was studied by direct replica transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and transmission electron diffraction (TED), respectively. Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) was utilized to verify DIMP absorption.

A micrograph of a typical discontinuous gas sensitive film whose average thickness is a 100\AA , is shown in Figure 3. The film's qualitative chemical composition was determined by indexing the corresponding TED. Consultation of the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) file indicated that a mixed phase of copper and cuprous oxide are present (no evidence of cupric oxide).

The motivation for comparing exposed and unexposed films using AES was to determine where DIMP is absorbed. Silicon nitride and silicon dioxide dielectric supports were used. Although the results are the same for each, the silicon nitride supported films yielded the clearest AES spectra (dielectric charging effects minimized). Figure 4 depicts an AES spectra of a DIMP exposed, silicon nitride surface located adjacent to the sensor's electrodes and gas sensitive film. An independent residual gas analysis indicated the presence of carbon monoxide, which likely accounts for the carbon (C) and oxygen (O). Figure 5 shows the AES spectra of the same sample, but now the Auger beam has been translated to the electrode gap region and focused (10 micron diameter) on the discontinuous film. The results show the superposition of the effects of the silicon nitride substrate (Si and N), the absorbed carbon monoxide, (C and O), the copper + cuprous oxide film (Cu and O), and most importantly, a phosphorus (P) transition which is present only for DIMP exposed samples.

Direct Current Conductivity Studies. Direct current bias studies were used to evaluate the DIMP sensitivity of the copper + cuprous oxide films. The films did not respond to either ultra-high purity Ar or N_2 , or when either was used as a carrier for DIMP. When laboratory air with relative humidity less than one percent is used as a carrier for DIMP, the film's conductivity changes are very small (less than 2 percent). However, with a relative humidity level greater than 2 percent, the DIMP reaction is

triggered and is reversible, as depicted in Figure 6.

The effect of electric field, temperature, and film thickness on DIMP sensitivity was evaluated. As a representative example, the isothermal current versus voltage characteristics of an exposed 100Å average thickness film are depicted in Figure 7. As the DIMP exposure concentration is increased, there is a slight, but nonuniform upward shift observed for each isotherm. A quantitative interpretation of the isotherms was accomplished by least-squares fitting a phenomenological relation of the form:

$$I = A(T,g)V + B(T,g)V^n \quad (1)$$

where I is the measured current

V is the applied voltage

n is an exponent which determines the type of non-ohmic behavior

A(T,g) is the ohmic coefficient which may be a function of temperature (T) and DIMP exposure (g)

B(T,g) is the non-ohmic coefficient which may be a function of temperature and DIMP exposure.

For metallic film samples with average thicknesses of 72Å, 100Å, and 157Å, the analysis of $[\Delta A/A]$, $[\Delta B/B]$, and their ratio, $S = [\Delta A/A]/[\Delta B/B]$, for conditions of constant temperature, film thickness, and exposure level revealed that:

1. $[\Delta A/A]$ is essentially constant with temperature changes (temperature independent), increases with decreasing film thickness, and increases with increasing DIMP exposure.
2. $[\Delta B/B]$ increases with increasing temperature (temperature dependent), increases with decreasing film thickness, and increases with increasing DIMP exposure.
3. $[\Delta B/B] > [\Delta A/A]$ at each temperature, film thickness, and DIMP exposure level.
4. S increases with increasing temperature, increases with decreasing film thickness, and increases with increasing DIMP exposure.

These trends suggest that operation where the B(T,g)-coefficient has a dominant effect (applied biases greater than

10 volts) would contribute toward optimizing sensitivity.

Plots of $\ln A(T,g)$ versus reciprocal absolute temperature are linear, and the values of the corresponding activation energies (E_a) compare very closely with those calculated from the conventional, low-bias direct current versus reciprocal absolute temperature plots. On the other hand, plots for the B(T,g)-coefficient are always non-linear. These results suggest that the $A(T,g)V = [\beta \exp(-E_a/kT)]V$ term can be interpreted in terms of a thermal activation process. Similarly, the $B(T,g)V^n$ term can be regarded as a non-activated field-injection (or hopping) conduction mechanism.

Hill [6] has analyzed direct current conduction mechanisms in dielectric supported discontinuous metallic film structures and presents an argument that does not require direct tunneling between islands, but advocates a conduction process via a large density of closely-spaced traps, impurities, or localized states near the conduction and valence band edges of the dielectric, while fewer, more-widely spaced states are located near the Fermi level. Hill proposes that electron transport between the islands is accomplished via successive electron tunneling jumps to neighboring trapping sites, and ultimately to an adjacent island. The fundamental advantage of this model is that it is not necessary to raise an electron to the conduction band of the substrate, and since the tunneling distance between traps is small, tunneling between islands whose spacings are greater than 30Å can be explained. Further, based upon the observed affinity of the metallic clusters for the DIMP + water complex, it is proposed that the number, distribution, and probability of occupancy of the trap and impurity states are favorably influenced by the contaminant absorption process. It is also reasonable to anticipate that the corresponding fluctuating surface dipole (charge) produced by the absorbed contaminants will act to modulate (lower) the potential barrier between metallic clusters.

As suggested by the experimental isothermal current versus voltage measurements and the least-squares fitted phenomenological model, the number of thermally activated charge carriers is independent of the applied voltage for $V < 10$ volts (Figure 7), but is enhanced by the absorption of the DIMP + water complex. On the other hand, the number of field-induced charge carriers for $V > 10$ volts (Figure 7) depends on both the applied voltage and DIMP absorption. Therefore, the following explanation is postulated for the associated transport mechanism.

Qualitatively for low temperatures and small fields, the number of thermally excited charge carriers is very low, as illustrated in Figure 8a. No carriers are excited at zero temperature and field since most trap and impurity sites below the Fermi level in the substrate are filled, and few charge carriers can be transferred from one site to another by tunneling.

At some critical temperature and near zero field, a finite population of carriers will be activated (thermally) above the Fermi level in the substrate. As depicted in Figure 8b, these carriers are free to hop from one trap site to another by a tunneling mechanism. This mechanism is activated because the charge carriers may not necessarily tunnel at a constant energy level. The density and distribution of the trap sites are attributable to the nature of the substrate (amorphous glass) and its electronic interaction with the carpet of the absorbed DIMP + water complex. When carriers can be thermally activated above the Fermi level of the substrate, this phenomenon distinctly implies that the tunneling current behaves according to the Arrhenius relationship $\{A(T,g)V = [\beta \exp(-E_a/kT)]V\}$ and represents the ohmic component of the total current. Since the experimental data reveals that the A-coefficient and the activation energy (E_a) are independent of temperature, the linear shifts between the $\ln A$ versus T^{-1} curves reflect the effect of the absorbed DIMP + water complex and can be attributed to the pre-exponential temperature-independent coefficient (β).

At low temperatures and when the field is increased, charges in the metal clusters may be injected into the trap sites in the insulator and hop from trap to trap and contribute to a current as depicted in Figure 8c. Additionally, when the temperature is not increased under the higher field conditions, the thermally activated mechanism can coexist with the non-activated process as illustrated in Figure 8d. The role of the absorbed DIMP + water complex is to enhance the number and occupancy of the trap sites.

For the non-ohmic, high-field component of the phenomenological model, a space-charge-limited current mechanism is suggested by the V^2 -dependency. The space-charge (Q) that can be forced into the insulator can be expressed as:

$$Q = CV \quad (2)$$

where Q is the space-charge injected into the substrate
C is the capacitance between the metallic clusters

V is the applied voltage.

For those charges which tunnel through the insulator via the trap sites, the space-charge-limited current (I_{sc}) can be expressed as:

$$I_{sc} = Qt^{-1} = CVt^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where t is the transit time between trap sites.

If D is the quantum mechanical tunneling transmission coefficient (tunneling probability), it is reasonable to expect that:

$$t \propto D^{-1} \quad (4)$$

In Neugebauer and Webb's [7] classical paper, they assumed that D was proportional to V when the potential barrier is not significantly perturbed by small fields. This approximation may also be applied in this situation since the fields used in this research were not large (1.2×10^4 V·cm⁻¹ maximum). Mostovetch and Vodar [8] report that for a potential barrier on the order of 1 eV and a distance (d) between trap sites of approximately 10Å, then, for the barrier to be lowered (ΔE) by 10^{-1} eV, a field $[F = (2 \cdot \Delta E) \cdot (de)^{-1}]$ of at least 2×10^5 V·cm⁻¹ is required. Thus, Eq. (4) can be expressed as:

$$t = kV^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where k is a constant of proportionality. Substituting Eq. (5) into Eq. (3) yields an expression similar to the non-ohmic term in Eq. (1). That is:

$$I_{sc} = B(T,g)V^2 \quad (6)$$

where B(T,g) is a coefficient of proportionality which is a function of temperature and DIMP exposure.

The nonlinear plots of $\ln B(T,g)$ versus T^{-1} for the experimental results suggest that B(T,g) is temperature dependent and is also significantly dependent upon the DIMP + water complex absorption. This situation implies that the absorbed contaminant favorable enhances the occupancy of the substrate's shallow trap density, and the experimental results reveal a maximum current flow under high temperature and large field conditions.

CONCLUSION

The modification of the electrical conductivity of thermally evaporated, discontinuous films of copper + cuprous oxide supported on a dielectric substrate caused by exposure to DIMP was investigated.

Direct replica transmission electron microscopy revealed the film's discontinuous island morphology. The associated electron diffraction measurements demonstrated that the films consist of a mixed phase of copper and cuprous oxide. Auger electron spectroscopy confirmed the preferential absorption of DIMP on the gas-sensitive film.

Isothermal, direct current versus voltage DIMP exposure profiles were least-squares fitted to an $I=AV+BV^2$ phenomenological model where $B=(0.01)A$. With respect to DIMP exposure, the $[\Delta A/A]$ -parameter, $[\Delta B/B]$ -parameter, and their ratio revealed that temperatures just less than 100°C , thin films (100\AA), and a large direct current bias (greater than 10 volts), evoked the strongest gas sensitivity. Plots of $\ln A$ versus reciprocal absolute temperature are linear (temperature independent). Corresponding plots of $\ln B$ are nonlinear (temperature dependent). The ohmic component suggests a thermal activation process. The non-ohmic component is indicative of a space-charge, field-injection mechanism. Both mechanisms operate together, which suggests that carriers are thermally excited, field induced, and transported via shallow trapping and impurity centers contributed by the substrate and carpet of the absorbed DIMP + water molecules.

REFERENCES

1. G. G. Guilbault, J. Affolter, Y. Tomita, and E. S. Kolesar, Jr. Piezoelectric crystal coating for detection of organophosphorus compounds, *Anal. Chem.*, 53 (1981) 2057.
2. T. Wagner-Jauregg, B. E. Hackley, T. A. Lies, O. O. Owen, and R. Proper, Model reactions of phosphorus containing enzyme activators, IV. The catalytic activity of diisopropyl fluorophosphate, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 77 (1955) 922.
3. R. Gustofson, S. Chaberek, and A. E. Martell, A kinetic study of the copper (II) chelate catalyzed hydrolysis of diisopropyl phosphorofluoridate, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 85 (1963) 598.
4. J. E. Morris and T. J. Coutts, Electrical conduction in discontinuous metal films: a discussion, *Thin Solid Films*, 47 (1977) 3.
5. Permeation Device, model 23-7392, GC Industries, Inc., Chatsworth, CA 91311.
6. R. M. Hill, Electrical conduction in ultra thin metal films II. experimental, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, A309 (1969) 397.
7. C. A. Neugebauer and M. B. Webb, Electrical conduction mechanism in ultrathin, evaporated metal films, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 33 (1962) 74.
8. N. Mostovetch and B. Vodar, Electrical conductivity of very thin metallic films evaporated in high vacuum, in *Semiconducting Materials*, Academic Press, NY, 1951, p.260.

Figure 1. Photograph of the 203 Micron Wide Electrode Gap.

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram of the Gas Generation and Delivery System.

Figure 3. TEM Micrograph of a 100\AA Average Thickness Copper Film (72,000 magnification).

Figure 4. AES Spectrum of the Silicon Nitride Surface Located Outside the Electrodes and Island Film Structure that was Exposed to DIMP.

Figure 5. AES Spectrum of the Evaporated Copper + Cuprous Oxide Islands in the Electrode Gap Region that were Exposed to DIMP -- Silicon Nitride Dielectric Support.

Figure 6. Response of a Copper + Cuprous Oxide Thin Film Electrode Structure to Alternating Challenges and Purges of DIMP Mixed with Laboratory Air.

Figure 7. Current versus Voltage Characteristics¹ for an Exposed (atmospheric pressure) 72Å Thin Film Electrode Structure Showing the Nine Discrete Temperature Profiles² [-20°C, -10, 0, 10, 20, 30, 50, 70, 90°C]

¹ Solid bullets represent the measured values, and the lines represent:

$$I = A(T,g)V + B(T,G)V^2.$$

² Uppermost curve relative to the current axis is the 90°C characteristic, the lower curve is the -20°C characteristic and the intermediate curves have a systematic correspondence with the intermediate temperatures.

(a)

(d)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. Energy Level Diagram of a Metal Cluster-Substrate-Metal Cluster System for: a) Zero Temperature and Field, b) Finite Temperature and a Small Field, c) Zero Temperature and a Large Field, d) Finite Temperature and a Large Field.

Key:

- empty trap
- filled trap
- transported carrier